

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10913411>

UDC 66.001.001.57:66.022:621.926/929

**DEVELOPMENT OF A METHOD FOR OPTIMIZATION
OF THE PROCESS OF ISOMERIZATION OF N-PARAFIN
HYDROCARBONS C5~C6 IN COMBINATION
WITH THEIR RECYCLING**

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Annotation: The most important requirements of the modern chemical, petrochemical and oil refining industries are the development of waste-free processes, maximum use of raw materials, activity of adsorbents and catalysts, intensification of chemical processes, creation of processes for reusing reagents, water and air in a closed system. In light of the above, adsorption processes with feedback (recirculation) acquire particular relevance. Adsorption methods are becoming available for many chemists of technological processes – isolating target components from mixtures, purifying wastewater and exhaust gases from toxic substances, drying gases and liquids, etc., thanks to the synthesis of new and modification of existing, including natural, adsorbents. Adsorption processes have been studied in detail by domestic and foreign scientists. However, a number of problems remain unresolved. Systems consisting of adsorption and chemical-technological blocks with feedback have not been studied. In the

field of development of scientific foundations of adsorption-technological processes with feedback, consisting in a mathematical description of processes in individual devices, material and energy flows between them, a systematic approach to modeling and optimization of these processes. The purpose of the work is to develop the scientific foundations of processes occurring in feedback systems consisting of adsorption and associated chemical-technological blocks

Keywords: n-pentane, n-hexane, isomerization, paraffins, hydrocarbons, recycling

РАЗРАБОТКА МЕТОДА ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ ПРОЦЕССА ИЗОМЕРИЗАЦИИ Н-ПАРАФИНОВЫХ УГЛЕВОДОРОДОВ C5~C6 В СОВМЕСТИИ С ИХ ПЕРЕРАБОТКОЙ

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Аннотация: Важнейшими требованиями современной химической, нефтехимической и нефтеперерабатывающей промышленности являются развитие безотходных процессов, максимальное использование сырья, активность адсорбентов и катализаторов, интенсификация химических процессов, создание процессов повторного использования реагентов, воды и воздух в закрытой системе. В свете вышесказанного особую актуальность приобретают процессы адсорбции с обратной связью

(рециркуляцией). Методы адсорбции становятся доступными для многих химиков технологических процессов – выделения целевых компонентов из смесей, очистки сточных вод и отходящих газов от токсичных веществ, осушки газов и жидкостей и т.д., благодаря синтезу новых и модификации существующих, в том числе природных, адсорбентов. Процессы адсорбции подробно изучены отечественными и зарубежными учеными. Однако ряд проблем остается нерешенным. Системы, состоящие из адсорбционного и химико-технологического блоков с обратной связью, не изучены. В области разработки научных основ адсорбционно-технологических процессов с обратной связью, заключающихся в математическом описании процессов в отдельных устройствах, потоках материалов и энергии между ними, системном подходе к моделированию и оптимизации этих процессов. Цель работы – разработка научных основ процессов, происходящих в системах с обратной связью, состоящих из адсорбционных и связанных с ними химико-технологических блоков.

Ключевые слова: н-пентан, н-гексан, изомеризация, парафины, углеводороды, рециклинг

Introduction: Achieving this goal required complex research, including: a) mathematical descriptions of individual processes in the apparatus and flows between them, expressed by the parameters of adsorption and associated isomerization blocks; b) development of mathematical models and optimization of different options for the systems under study, taking into account the loading of devices and recycle flows, the amount of adsorbent required to separate the recycle from the reaction product, material and energy flows between devices; c) creation of methods based on such research design of enlarged adsorption-technological processes. During the work, the following tasks were solved: Determination of technological and design parameters of the system based on experimental data and developed models and algorithms;

1. Application of the obtained scientific results to various similar processes with the development of methods that help reduce the stages of their research and implementation using the following process as an example: separation of n-paraffin hydrocarbons from gasoline by

continuous adsorption in combination with their isomerization and recycling.

2. Justification of the economic efficiency of the process under study.

3. Using the results obtained to develop methods for engineering calculations of the process and installation. The scientific novelty of the work lies in the creation of the scientific foundations of a systematic approach to modeling and optimization of the system under consideration. To model such a system, equations have been derived that take into account parameters that allow calculating the adsorber loading, isomerization of recycle n-paraffins at the outlet of the adsorber, the amount of adsorbent required to separate the recycle from the reaction product, material and energy flows between devices and subsystems, the number of cycles to achieve a steady state process of cleaning the environment from impurities in a closed system, adsorption isotherms, capillary condensation and the influence on them of the structural characteristics of the adsorbent, the true porosity of the layer and the righteousness of the cross-section of the adsorbent layer, the pressure drop of the adsorbent flow and the influence on it of the effect of stationary porosity of the adsorbent layer, variable recirculation coefficient, kinetic coefficient of adsorption depending on the degree of filling of the adsorbent, "aging" adsorbent, etc.

Using these equations, unified mathematical models of adsorption technological systems with feedback have been developed: processes of continuous adsorption separation of reaction products from recycle for different operating modes of the adsorber. The effectiveness of using the recommended recycle method in the field of adsorption has been established, with the use of which the maximum equilibrium activity of the adsorbent, and, consequently, its productivity, increases and can reach their maximum value.

It is shown that when solving model equations, the Papilis method (with the help of which a numerical inverse transition from images of the Laplace-Carson transform to their original is carried out) is applicable with sufficient accuracy for practice. A technique is proposed that allows, using periodic adsorption data, to calculate parameters and design a continuous adsorption process with a moving adsorbent layer without conducting an experiment.

Experimental part. Outlining the practical value, it should be noted that the method of system modeling and optimization of adsorption-isomerization processes with recycling used in the work can be used for any processes of the corresponding type. As examples, the work presents the results of a study of a number of practically important processes with the aim of: checking the obtained new equations, models and calculation algorithms, classifying processes from the point of view of modeling, and bringing them to practical use.

A system model has been developed for the process of separating n-paraffin hydrocarbons C5-Sb from gas condensate by continuous adsorption with a moving layer of adsorbent in combination with their isomerization and recirculation of the isomerizate into the adsorber, with the help of which technological and design parameters are calculated, the optimal mode is found, and the economic efficiency of the system is calculated. It has been established that when the system operates with isomerate recycle, it is possible to reduce the yield of n-paraffins to almost zero and thereby significantly increase the efficiency of the process. The annual economic effect from the introduction of this process in the Republic of Azerbaijan alone can amount to 7.3 million mana/year.

The development of waste-free production is the most important requirement of our time. In this regard, adsorption and recycling processes become particularly relevant. By adsorption, valuable components are separated from mixtures of petroleum products, wastewater and exhaust gases are purified from toxic substances, and gases and liquids are dried.

The use of the recirculation method in adsorption processes contains great opportunities for the further development of adsorption technology.

This section presents the results of optimization of this process using experimental data and the model given in the previous section [1-5].

The extraction of a mixture of n-pentane and n-hexane from the stream was carried out at different temperatures and corresponding adsorbent and raw materials (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Dependence of the degree of extraction on the adsorption temperature:

1-n C₆H₁₂; 2-n. C₆H₁₄. Ratio of adsorbent to raw material Δ – η = 8: 1; x – η = 10: 1; o – η = 12: 1

Figure 2 – Yield of C₅-C₆ isomers. The influence of temperature (α) and space velocity (δ, at 350 0C) on the isomerization reaction of pentane – hexane fraction on gas condensate (P = 30 atm, H₂/feed = 3)

As experimental studies show, the highest degree of extraction was obtained at a temperature of 70°C and the ratio of adsorbent to raw material η = 12:1.

$$H_{\eta} = \frac{C_{\text{пр}} \cdot \dot{g}_{\text{пр}} - (C_{\text{св}} \dot{g}_{\text{св}} + S_k)}{C_{\text{св}} \cdot \dot{g}_{\text{св}} + S_k}$$

where the numerator reflects the profit from the sale of finished products, and the denominator reflects the total costs; $C_{\text{пр}}$, $C_{\text{св}}$ – cost of product and fresh raw materials, man/t; $\dot{g}_{\text{пр}}$, $\dot{g}_{\text{св}}$ – respectively, the quantities of manufactured finished products and incoming fresh raw materials, e/year; S_k – total production costs for its system, including the cost of equipment, equipment costs, labor, pumping flows, depreciation charges, etc., man/year. The calculations record the quantities of incoming fresh raw materials, output products and the cost of fresh raw materials. These quantities are established as a result of global optimization of the material and heat flows of those regions (installations) with which the adsorption and isomerization blocks considered in this work are associated [6-9].

Results and discussions: The compiled program for optimizing this process using a computer takes into account the variation of controlled parameters, which include the temperatures of the adsorber, desorber, isomerization region reactor and the flow rates of the adsorbent and the mixture of fresh raw materials with isomerate. Depending on the change in the controlled parameters, the concentrations of n-pentane, n-hexane at the outlet of the reactor, at the outlet of the desorber, the degree of use of the maximum activity of the adsorbent and, of course, the entire range of components of n-paraffin, isoparaffin and cyclic hydrocarbons (aromatic and naphthenic) change. at the outlet of the adsorber (in the product of a combined installation). The contact time of the adsorbent with the molecules of the adsorbed components depends on the controlled parameters – the flow rates of the adsorbent and the mixture of fresh raw materials with isomerate. In addition to the above values, the program for optimizing the combined adsorption and isomerization process also takes into account the cost of the catalyst, adsorbent, installations with all instruments, energy spent on increasing or decreasing the temperatures of the adsorbent, catalyst and hydrocarbon mixture, pumping products, raw materials and transport gas, depreciation of the installation, instruments, catalyst, adsorbent, etc. As a result of optimization, the highest rate of profit was obtained equal to 0.6030 with optimal values of operating parameters, controllable and output values given in Table 1.

Table 1 – Optimal values of operating parameters

Parameter name Designation Size Optimal	Parameter name Designation Size Optimal	Parameter name Designation Size Optimal	Parameter name Designation Size Optimal
Adsorption temperature	T_1	K	373
Desorption temperature	T_2		603
Isomerization reaction temperature	T_5		603
Concentration of n-pentane and n-hexane at the reactor outlet	$C_{51}^{(5)}, C_{51}^{(6)}$	kg/kg	0,300 0,028
Concentration of n-C ₅ and n-C ₆ in fresh batch	$C_{01}^{(5)}, C_{01}^{(6)}$		0,306 0,134
Concentration of n-C ₅ and n-C ₆ at the inlet to the reactor	$C_{25}^{(5)}, C_{25}^{(6)}$		0,700 0,1905
Concentration of n-C ₅ and n-C ₆ at the outlet to the reactor	$C_{out}^{(5)}, C_{out}^{(6)}$		0,03 0,0145
Specific heat capacities of the adsorbent and the mixture of n-C ₅ and n-Sb	$C_a, C^{(5,6)}$	kcal/kg °C	0,2 0,58
Fresh loading of n-C ₅ -C ₆ components into the adsorber	$\dot{g}_{51}^{(5)}, \dot{g}_{51}^{(6)}$	kg/ hour	1,8214 0,7976
Fresh loading of a mixture of all raw material components (in the same quantity, taking into account losses, the product of the combined process is obtained)	$\dot{g}_{CB}$		5,9524
Linear1 flow rate in the adsorber	v	m/hour	5,785
Ratio of adsorbent to raw material	η	-	12:1
The amount of expenses spent on depreciation of the installation, adsorbent,		man / hour	0,08698

Parameter name Designation Size Optimal	Parameter name Designation Size Optimal	Parameter name Designation Size Optimal	Parameter name Designation Size Optimal
catalyst, salaries, pumping flows, etc.			
Cost of fresh raw materials and product	C_{nv}, C_{pr}	man/kg	0,02694 0,072
Energy cost	C_q	man/kcal	$0,282 \cdot 10^{15}$

The heat capacity of CaA up to 100°C is 0.2 kcal/kg °C. The same for a palladium containing catalyst – 0.24 kcal/kg °C. Dimensions: adsorber – L – 0.90 m; D = 0.15 m; desorber – L = 1.2 m; D – 0.20 m; refrigerator – L = 0.6 m; D = 0.075 m; dryer L = 0.75 m; D – 0.1 m; reactor L – 0.70 m; D = 0.025 m.

As a result of the calculations, the optimal values of the parameters were obtained: 1) the specific cost of the product is 44.32 man/t; 2) profit from the sale of finished products 27.08 man/t; 3) the payback period of the installation is less than 2 years; 4) the expected profit based on gas gasoline resources amounting to 270 thousand tons/year is 7.312 million mana/year.

Conclusion:

1. For the first time, the possibility of calculating with sufficient accuracy based on individual isotherms of adsorption of C5-C6 n-paraffins on CaA zeolite and the adsorption of these hydrocarbons from a mixture of C5-C6 n-paraffins with isoparaffins was demonstrated. This method is cost-effective and speeds up experimental research.

2. The results of experimental and theoretical studies of the process of adsorption separation of C5-Cb n-paraffins in a fluidized bed of CaA zeolite are presented.

3. Processes in a system consisting of a continuous adsorption block and isomerization blocks were studied.

4. A complete mathematical model of the process of separating n-paraffin hydrocarbons C5-C6 by continuous adsorption in combination with their isomerization and recycling has been developed, with the help of which technological and design parameters are calculated, the optimal process mode is determined, the economic efficiency of the system is calculated and used in design and management integrated installations and processes.

5. The process of isolation and isomerization of C5-C6 n-paraffin hydrocarbons in combination with their recycling has been optimized.

6. It was found that the profit from the sale of finished products in the case of the optimal option is 27.08 man/t, and the highest rate of profit was obtained in the amount of 60%.

Expected savings from the implementation of the recommended process based on gas gasoline resources amounting to 270 thousand per year will be 7.312 million mana per year.

Bibliography

[1] Study of the crystallization process of iron-containing zeolites / A.V. Vosmerikov, L.L. Korobitsyna, N.V. Arbuzova, V.I. Radomskaya // *Journal of Inorganic Chemistry*. – 2002. T. 47. No. 11.

[2] Confined Carbon Mediating Dehydroaromatization of Methane over Mo/ZSM-5 N. Kosinov, A.S.G. Wijkema, E.A. Uslamin [et al.] // *Angewandte Chemie*. – 2017. V. 57. No. 4. 1016-1020 p.

[3] Comparative study of direct methylation of benzene with methane on cobalt exchanged ZSM-5 and ZSM-11 zeolites / P. Hu, K. Nakamura, H. Matsubara [et al.] // *Catalysis A: General*. – 2020. V. 601. No. 5. 117661 p.

[4] Specifications. Zeolite catalyst IK-17-M. TU 2177-008-07622236-2006 LU.

[5] Direct Insertion of Methane into C3–C4 Paraffins over Zeolite Catalysts: Start to the Development of New One-step Catalytic Processes for the Gas-to-Liquid Transformation. /G.V. Echevsky, E.G. Kodenev, O.V. Kikhtyanin, V.N. Parmon // *Applied Catalysis A: General*. – 2004. Vol. 258. No. 2. 159-171 p.

[6] Echevsky G.V. Unconventional ways of producing motor fuels and valuable chemical products from various hydrocarbon fractions / G.V. Echevsky // *Russ. chem. and.* – 2003. T. XLVII. No. 6. 30-35 p.

[7] New energy and resource-saving technology for producing high-quality motor fuels from middle oil distillates and gas condensates – BIMT / G.V. Echevsky, O.V. Klimov, O.V. Kikhtyanin [et al.] // *Catalysis in industry*. – 2003. No. 2. 60-66 p.

[8] Yusubov F.V. “The process of adsorption de-aromatization of paraffins (sfr. 473-592k): modeling and optimal design” Abstract of the

dissertation for the degree of candidate of technical sciences. / F.V. Yusubov – Baku, 1992. Art. 3-5.

[9] Erofeev V.I. Production of high-octane gasoline from straight-run gasoline using modified ZSM-5 zeolites / V.I. Erofeev, I.S. Khomyakov, L.A. Egorova // Theoretical foundations of chemical technology. – 2014. Т. 48. No. 1. 77-82 p.

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Исследование процесса кристаллизации железосодержащих цеолитов / А.В. Восмериков, Л.Л. Коробицына, Н.В. Арбузова, В.И. Радомская // Журнал неорганической химии. – 2002. Т. 47. № 11.

[2] Confined Carbon Mediating Dehydroaromatization of Methane over Mo/ZSM-5 N. Kosinov, A.S.G. Wijkema, E.A. Uslamin [et al.] // *Angewandte Chemie*. – 2017. V. 57. No 4. 1016-1020 p.

[3] Comparative study of direct methylation of benzene with methane on cobalt exchanged ZSM-5 and ZSM-11 zeolites / P. Hu, K. Nakamura, H. Matsubara [et al.] // *Catalysis A: General*. – 2020. V. 601. No 5. 117661 p.

[4] Технические условия. Цеолитный катализатор ИК-17-М. ТУ 2177-008-07622236- 2006 ЛУ.

[5] Direct Insertion of Methane into C3–C4 Paraffins over Zeolite Catalysts: Start to the Development of New One-step Catalytic Processes for the Gas-to-Liquid Transformation. / G.V. Echevsky, E.G. Kodenev, O.V. Kikhtyanin, V.N. Parmon // *Applied Catalysis A: General*. – 2004. Vol. 258. No 2. 159-171 p.

[6] Ечевский Г.В. Нетрадиционные пути получения моторных топлив и ценных химических продуктов из различных углеводородных фракций / Г.В. Ечевский // *Рос. хим. ж.* – 2003. Т. XLVII. № 6. 30-35 с.

[7] Новая энергия и ресурсосберегающая технология получения высококачественных моторных топлив из средних нефтяных дистиллятов и газовых конденсатов – БИМТ / Г.В. Ечевский, О.В. Климов, О.В. Кихтярин [и др.] // *Катализ в промышленности*. – 2003. № 2. 60-66 с.

[8] Юсубов Ф.В. «Процесс адсорбционной деароматизации парафинов (сфр. 473-592к): моделирование и оптимальное

проектирование» Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата технических наук. / Ф.В. Юсубов – Баку, 1992. ст. 3-5.

[9] Ерофеев В.И. Получение высокооктановых бензинов из прямогонных бензинов на модифицированных цеолитах ZSM-5 / В.И. Ерофеев, И.С. Хомяков, Л.А. Егорова // Теоретические основы химической технологии. – 2014. Т. 48. № 1. 77-82 с.

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Поступила в редакцию 04.01.2024

Принята к публикации 26.01.2024

Для цитирования:

Guliyeva S.N., Mirzəyev B.A., Mammadova Z.E. Development of a method for optimization of the process of isomerization of n-paraffin hydrocarbons C5~C6 in combination with their recycling // Инновационные научные исследования. 2024. № 1-1(38). С. 5-16. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>